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Green Building Report:

Comparative Energy Analysis of Central Business Districts (CBDs) in Mumbai, London, and Bangkok: Identifying Sustainable Solutions for Mumbai's CBD

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Abstract

This report compares energy efficiency strategies and policies in the central business districts (CBDs) of London and Bangkok and provides recommendations for improving energy efficiency in Mumbai's CBD. The analysis reveals that London has a comprehensive and integrated approach to energy efficiency, while Bangkok is making progress but requires further action. The report suggests several key solutions for Mumbai, including stricter building regulations, an emissions trading scheme, smart infrastructure investments, and sustainable transportation promotion. Other recommendations include adopting an ambitious carbon neutrality target, increasing the use of renewable energy, promoting public awareness, introducing a green tax rebate system, and implementing Energy Performance Certificates. By considering these recommendations, Mumbai CBD can enhance its energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and pave the way for a sustainable future.

Keywords : Energy efficiency, Central Business Districts, CBD, London, Bangkok, Mumbai, building regulations, emissions trading, smart infrastructure, carbon neutrality, renewable energy, public awareness, green tax rebate, Energy Performance Certificates.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Climate change has become a pressing global issue, necessitating immediate action to mitigate its adverse effects. Climate change is a major threat to cities around the world (McCOMAS & SHANAHAN, 1999). Mumbai Central Business District (CBD) is no exception. Mumbai's CBD, as a bustling urban center, faces unique challenges in addressing climate change and reducing carbon emissions. The city is already experiencing the effects of climate change, such as rising temperatures, increased flooding, and more extreme weather events (*Mumbai Air Quality Index (AQI) and India Air Pollution 2023*). These effects are likely to get worse in the future.

In order to tackle this global situation countries including UK, France, Norway and New Zealand committed and working towards policies to achieve zero emission by 2050 (FALKNER, 2016, page 1107). Similar commitment and pathway is required to be followed by the developing countries with megacities. In 2020, the city's buildings were responsible for emitting 11.5 million tons of carbon dioxide, making them the city's largest source of greenhouse gas emissions in Dubai (DEWA, 2021). Hence this report aims to achieve a set of recommendations and solutions for the developing countries through comparative studies. As commercial spaces and real estates are having the most carbon emission around 40% (Carlin, 2022), this report focuses on the comparative study of the Central Business District situated in Mumbai, London and Bangkok. The reason behind choosing CBD from these three cities is the economical and geographical similarities as shown in the table below:

Factor	Mumbai	London	Bangkok
Population	21 million	9.3 million	10.5 million
Area	2.1 square kilometres	2.9 square kilometres	1.8 square kilometres
Main industries	Finance, trade, commerce, media, IT	Finance, insurance, law, media, tourism	Finance, trade, commerce, tourism, manufacturing
Major landmarks	World Trade Center Mumbai, Oberoi Towers, Gateway of India	St. Paul's Cathedral, Tower of London, Buckingham Palace	Baiyoke Tower II, Grand Hyatt Erawan Bangkok, Wat Pho
Transportation	Mumbai Suburban Railway, Mumbai Metro, Mumbai Monorail	London Underground, Docklands Light Railway, Overground	Bangkok Skytrain, BTS, MRT
Climate	Hot and humid	Temperate	Hot and humid
Challenges	Traffic congestion, air pollution, poverty	High cost of living, crime, terrorism	Traffic congestion, air pollution, flooding
Opportunities	Growing economy, rising middle class, increasing investment	Global financial hub, cultural and historical attractions	Tourism, manufacturing, growing economy

Table 1. Made by Author

Source: Mumbai: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Mumbai> London: <https://www.britannica.com/place/London> and Bangkok: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Bangkok>

Furthermore as Mumbai is struggling with the pollution and energy efficiency issues which resulted its PM2.5 to be 6.7 times higher than the WHO recommended (*Mumbai Air Quality Index (AQI) and India Air Pollution 2023*). This report aims to find the solutions for Mumbai by comparing it with CBDs of London and Bangkok.

Mumbai CBD is a densely populated area that is home to a large number of buildings. These buildings consume a significant amount of energy, which contributes to climate change. In 2020, the city's buildings were responsible for emitting 11.5 million tonnes of carbon dioxide, making them the city's largest source of greenhouse gas emissions. Mumbai being the financial capital of India and having the second most largest population of over 20 million, faces significant challenges in meeting its growing demand while ensuring sustainability and energy efficiency (Singh,2019). This megacity with the second-largest population in India and the sixth-largest population in the world has a very diverse energy consumption pattern as well as similarly diverse production of energy. Figure 1 shows the pie chart distribution of energy consumption by different sectors in Mumbai.

Figure 1. Energy consumption distribution in Mumbai Made by Author, Data Source : <https://www.greenbuildingadvisor.com/article/energy-use-by-buildings>

As per Figure 1 it is visible the residential sector dominates the energy consumption in Mumbai, similarly having a look at the energy mix in Figure 2 of Mumbai it is quite visible that the energy produced and being used is highly dominated by thermal energy.

Figure 2.Type of Energy mix in Mumbai. Made by Author, Data Source: <https://mcap.mcgm.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Energy-Buildings.pdf>

Referring to figure 2 this report highlights the dominance of thermal energy being the most used source of energy which is currently and even for the long run is not good for Mumbai(WRI, 2019).. Hence the energy consumed in Mumbai relies heavily on fossil fuels, particularly coal and natural gas. Fossil fuel combustion contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution, affecting both local air quality and global climate change. The poor status of the air quality as per AQI India states the current PM 2.5 concentration in Mumbai which is 3.7 times above the recommended limit given by the WHO 24hrs air quality guidelines value. Furthermore, the Residential and Commercial & Institutional buildings emissions are estimated to go up 3.3 times by 2050 in a business-as-usual scenario (WRI, 2019). Currently Energy and Building sector is responsible for over 60% of Mumbai’s total GHG emissions as shown in figure 3.

Figure 3.GHG Emission by different cause in Mumbai. Made by Author, Data Source: <https://mcap.mcgm.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Energy-Buildings.pdf>

Similarly with the overall situation of Mumbai, the Central Business District (CBD) of Mumbai also faces the issues of over-dependency on thermal energy rather than green and sustainable energy(WRI, 2019). The CBD of Mumbai is situated in Nariman point, and all the big companies’ head offices are situated there. Mumbai's Central Business District (CBD) is a vibrant economic hub that is vital to the city's commercial and financial activity. The CBD, Mumbai's business center, is home to a plethora of corporate offices, financial institutions, commercial organizations, and government agencies. However, the CBD consumes a significant amount of energy, posing issues in terms of energy efficiency and sustainability.

Commercial buildings, transport, and associated infrastructure account for the majority of the CBD's energy use. Commercial buildings in the CBD use a lot of energy for lighting, air conditioning, heating, and running technological equipment. Through fuel burning, the transportation industry, including private automobiles and public transit, contributes to energy consumption. The CBD's high population density, congestion, and vertical construction increase energy demands even more. The ageing infrastructure also is one the issues directly affecting the energy efficiency of the district. Refer to figure 4 below which shows a significant amount of stationary GHG emissions by commercial space Mumbai.

- Manufacturing Industries and construction (12%)
- Commercial, institutional buildings and facilities (37%)
- Residential (51%)

Figure 4. Stationary GHG emission by different sectors in Mumbai. Made by Author, Data Source: <https://mcap.mcg.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Energy-Buildings.pdf>

1.2 Objectives and Scope of the Research

The objective of this report is to examine Mumbai's CBD energy efficiency and to propose new solutions based on case studies from CBD London and CBD Bangkok. In this project, our aim is to conduct a comprehensive examination of the energy efficiency landscape in Mumbai's Central Business District (CBD). Our analysis will delve into various aspects, including energy consumption patterns, sectoral breakdowns, and the constraints and possibilities associated with energy efficiency. To gain valuable insights, we will closely study effective energy efficiency projects implemented in cities such as London and Bangkok. By exploring their tactics, policies, programs, and best practices, we can extract major takeaways and success factors applicable to Mumbai's CBD.

Armed with these findings, we will propose innovative solutions tailored to address the challenges of poor energy efficiency and high greenhouse gas emissions in Mumbai's CBD. Our recommendations will be informed by the comprehensive report and the valuable lessons learned from the case studies. The report is intended for policymakers, urban planners, and stakeholders involved in urban sustainability and climate change mitigation. The findings and recommendations of the report can help these stakeholders to develop and implement policies and plans that will improve energy efficiency in Mumbai CBD.

1.2.1 Specific Goals

The primary objective of this report is to thoroughly examine the energy efficiency landscape in Mumbai's Central Business District (CBD) and establish specific goals. Firstly, we aim to identify the current state of energy efficiency in the Mumbai CBD, shedding light on its strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, we intend to assess the challenges faced in enhancing energy efficiency while exploring the opportunities available for improvement. To derive valuable insights and learn from successful endeavors, we will extensively analyze best practices from other cities renowned for their notable achievements in energy efficiency. Case studies of London and Bangkok will be carefully examined, highlighting their tactics, strategies, policies, and programs that have effectively enhanced energy efficiency. Building upon the knowledge gained from these case studies, we will conduct an in-depth analysis to determine the key takeaways and success factors applicable to the Mumbai CBD. This analysis will serve as a foundation for proposing innovative solutions specifically tailored to address the unique challenges of poor energy efficiency and high greenhouse gas emissions in the CBD.

The structure of the report will be organized in a coherent manner to ensure clarity and comprehension. It will commence with an introduction, providing an overview of the report's objectives and scope. A comprehensive literature review will follow, synthesizing existing research on energy efficiency in CBDs. The subsequent section will delve into the case studies of London and Bangkok, examining their approaches and outcomes in detail. Through a meticulous analysis of the findings, we will extract crucial insights and highlight the most pertinent information. Drawing upon the collective knowledge gathered, the report will then present a range of proposed solutions specifically designed to enhance energy efficiency in the Mumbai CBD.

These recommendations will be firmly rooted in the report's analysis and the lessons learned from the case studies. Finally, the report will conclude by summarizing its key findings, emphasizing the significance of energy efficiency in the Mumbai CBD, and presenting recommendations for future research in this critical field. Throughout the report, a clear and concise writing style will be employed to ensure accessibility for a broad audience. Moreover, the data and evidence from the case studies will be incorporated to substantiate the report's findings effectively.

2. Methodology

Figure 5 showing Methodology step-wise. Source: Author

The methodology of this report will be a mixed-methods approach, which will involve data collection, case study analysis, and comparative analysis.

Data Collection: The first step in the methodology will be to collect relevant data on energy consumption, energy efficiency initiatives, policies, and socio-economic factors in CBD of Mumbai. This will include collecting data from government reports, energy regulatory bodies, research institutions, and other reliable sources. Data on energy consumption by different sectors in Mumbai will be obtained to understand the current energy profile of the city.

Case Study Analysis: The second step in the methodology will be to conduct two case studies on the energy efficiency of CBDs in London and Bangkok. These case studies will examine the successful energy efficiency initiatives that have been implemented in these cities, as London and Bangkok is already on a successful pathway to achieve zero emission (Pathways to net zero carbon by 2030,2023). The case studies will provide valuable insights into the best practices, challenges faced, and lessons learned, which can be applied to Mumbai's context.

Comparative Analysis: The third step in the methodology will be to conduct a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency in CBDs in Mumbai, London, and Bangkok. This will involve comparing the data collected from the case studies and identifying similarities and differences between the three cities. The comparative analysis will help identify relevant solutions and strategies that can be adapted to Mumbai's unique context.

Recommendations: The fourth and final step in the methodology will be to formulate actionable recommendations for policymakers, urban planners, businesses, and other stakeholders in CBD of Mumbai. These recommendations will encompass policy measures, technological interventions, stakeholder engagement strategies, and finance mechanisms. The recommendations will be designed to address the specific energy efficiency challenges identified in CBD Mumbai and promote sustainable development in the District. The methodology of this report is designed to be comprehensive and rigorous. The data collection, case study analysis, and comparative analysis will provide a solid foundation for the formulation of recommendations. The recommendations will be designed to be practical and implementable.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Carbon Neutrality by 2050 for CBDs:

The target of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050 has gained global recognition and has been adopted by many countries and cities, including the cities with the CBDs of this report. This target requires the implementation of various measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, such as enhancing building efficiency, adopting renewable energy sources, and promoting sustainable transportation (IEA, 2020; McKinsey & Company, 2019).

Image 1: Showing Countries on world map committed to carbon neutral goal. Source: <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/sp/race-to-net-zero-carbon-neutral-goals-by-country/>

3.2 Overview of CBD Mumbai (Nariman Point)

Image 2: Showing Geographical Position of CBD Mumbai. Source: [google. Maps](https://www.google.com/maps), edited by author

The CBD of Mumbai also shown in image 1 is situated in the heart of Mumbai also known as Nariman point. The total area of the CBD is 621,072 m² and it consists of 200 buildings including approx. 27 skyscrapers. This Nariman point is the subject of the analysis in the whole report, it's a well known place and being the business hub of India for more than 75 years now is one of the main reasons of selection, this will be mentioned as CBD Mumbai in the report. The maximum number of buildings at the project location has 4-6 floors which accounts to approx.. 59% of total buildings while the minimum number of buildings (Kumar Singh, 2013). While the minimal number of structures observed has 10 stories or more, which accounts for only 1% of the total. This is due to the fact that most buildings portray architecture that was erected many years ago with a maximum height of 5 to 6 floors only (Kumar Singh, 2013).

There are more prospects of redeveloping ancient buildings in our project region and constructing them with all amenities included, making the best use of the available property (Kumar Singh,2013). As per (*WRI India & Environment Status Report, 2020*) the total electricity demand of Mumbai is 3400-3600 MW, hence considering the data from figure 1 which states that 37% of the total energy consumption in Mumbai is consumed by commercial sector, this report achieves the number of 1295 MW approx. to be consumed by CBD Mumbai which is 37% 3500MW. Furthermore considering 1295 MW consumption of CBD Mumbai and as per *WRI India & Environment Status Report 2020* Energy mix data as shown in figure 2, the following table provides the overview of the energy profile in CBD Mumbai:

No.	Energy type	Provision in Percent(%)	Provision in MW
1	Thermal	95.34	1234,653
2	Wind	2.10	27,195
3	Hydro	1.86	24,087
4	Solar	0.70	9,065

Table 1: Showing overview of the energy profile of CBD Mumbai, Source: Author

3.3 Challenges in Energy efficiency of CBD Mumbai

3.3.1 Over dependency on Thermal Energy

CBD Mumbai situated in Nariman point has skyscrapers and is the one of the oldest commercial hub in Mumbai, thus it has multiple ageing infrastructure which is one the major challenges towards energy efficiency. As seen in table 1 over dependency on Thermal energy which is mostly coal and natural gas is also one of the challenges being faced by this district. This high dependency of grid on fossil fuel based thermal power is the main reason behind the extreme GHG emissions as seen in fig 3 and fig 4. This high dependency on thermal energy (Tembhekar , 2021) also costs more and harm this district economically on a longer run. Even though the green energy like solar panels is being used but its highly decentralized and unregulated which in term fails its purpose. To fulfil this big demand of energy in commercial sector the establishment of

coal powered electricity plants are increasing expanding around Mumbai which is increasing coal pollution to a fatal level (Tembhekar , 2021).

Image 3: Showing Coal energy plants around Mumbai. Source: <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/mumbai/mumbai-95-of-citys-power-comes-from-coal-ghg-big-concern/articleshow/86627697.cms> and also showing bad air quality due to these plants, Source: <https://www.igair.com/us/india/maharashtra/mumbai>

3.3.2 Ageing infrastructure and eco-unfriendly architecture

CBD Mumbai features a large number of older commercial buildings that were built several decades ago for e.g. The Express tower which was built back in 1972. These structures frequently lack modern energy-saving technologies, materials, and designs. Inadequate insulation, poor HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems, and outdated electrical systems all contribute to higher energy usage and increased GHG emissions. Furthermore, CBD Mumbai has many commercial buildings featuring poor floor designs and make excessive use of space.

Natural lighting and ventilation are compromised by large floor plates and deep building layouts. This necessitates a high reliance on artificial lighting and air conditioning, both of which increase energy consumption and carbon emissions. This inconsiderate architecture started around just after the independence of Indian in 1947 was still continued as the Mumbai was becoming the commercial hub and economical aspect was preferred more than anything at that development phase (Bhatia, 2023). Mumbai is also lacking behind in having LEEDS certified commercial spaces and only has 164 certifications (GBIG, 2023) till the date, which is comparatively very low considering the density of the buildings.

3.4 Current Initiatives and policies

The whole of the Mumbai Metropolitan region is divided into the following 7 zone (*Development control regulations for MMR 2016-2036*, 2016):

1. Urbanisable Zone: This zone is intended for development of residential, commercial, and industrial activities. It is the most densely populated zone in the MMR, and it accounts for the majority of the region's economic activity.
2. Industrial Zone: This zone is intended for the development of heavy industries. It is located on the outskirts of the MMR, and it is home to a number of large industrial estates.
3. Institutional Zone: This zone is intended for the development of educational, research, and medical institutions. It is located in the heart of the MMR, and it is home to a number of universities, hospitals, and research centers.

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4. Green Zone 1: This zone is intended for the development of parks, gardens, and other open spaces. It is located in the outer areas of the MMR, and it is home to a number of natural habitats.
 5. Green Zone 2: This zone is intended for the development of agriculture and forestry. It is located in the outermost areas of the MMR, and it is home to a number of villages and tribal communities.
 6. Forest Zone: This zone is intended for the protection of forests and wildlife. It is located in the outermost areas of the MMR, and it is home to a number of important ecosystems.
 7. Coastal Wetlands Zone: This zone is intended for the protection of coastal wetlands. It is located along the coast of the MMR, and it is home to a number of important habitats for birds and other wildlife.

The CBD Mumbai comes under definition of the Urbanisable Zone (*Development control regulations for MMR 2016-2036, 2016*) which has its own set of policies regarding the energy efficiency made in 2016 by MMRDA. The Mumbai Metropolitan Region Development Authority (MMRDA) is responsible for the planning and development of the MMR. The MMRDA has developed a Master Plan for the MMR, which outlines the future development of the region. The Master Plan includes a number of policies and initiatives that are designed to improve the energy efficiency of the MMR. One of the key policies in the Master Plan is the promotion of green buildings. The MMRDA has developed a number of incentives to encourage the construction of green buildings in the MMR(*Development control regulations for MMR 2016-2036, 2016*).

Another key policy in the Master Plan is the promotion of sustainable transportation. The MMRDA has developed a number of initiatives to promote sustainable transportation in the MMR. The MMRDA is also working to improve the energy efficiency of existing buildings. The MMRDA has developed a number of programs to help building owners and tenants improve the energy efficiency of their buildings. The MMRDA is committed to improving the energy efficiency of the Mumbai Metropolitan Region. The MMRDA is also working to implement a number of policies and initiatives that are designed to make the MMR a more sustainable region(*Development control regulations for MMR 2016-2036, 2016*).

4. Case Studies

4.1 CBD, London

London's Central Business District (CBD) is a bustling and energetic concentration of commercial activity in the city's heart. The CBD is located in the heart of London and encompasses various neighbourhoods, including the City of London, Canary Wharf, and sections of Westminster. This prime location is a hub for many enterprises, financial institutions, and corporate offices. It is an important centre for commerce and trade since it is home to big banks, law firms, multinational corporations, and a variety of professional services. The skyline of London's CBD is stunning, featuring prominent skyscrapers such as the Gherkin, the Shard, and One Canada Square (GLA, 2008).

Image 4. Central Business District , Canary Wharf London, Data Source: <https://mcap.mcgm.gov.in/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/Energy-Buildings.pdf>

4.1.1 Energy Efficiency Strategies and Policies in CBD London

Energy efficiency methods and policies are critical in supporting sustainable development and lowering greenhouse gas emissions in central business districts (CBDs) worldwide. As a worldwide financial and commercial powerhouse, London has adopted a number of initiatives to improve energy efficiency inside its CBD. This section will provide an overview of the energy efficiency methods and policies put in place in London's CBD. The development of energy-efficient buildings is one of the primary initiatives used in London's CBD. To ensure that new buildings and large renovations adhere to high energy efficiency requirements, the city has created severe building regulations and energy performance standards (Greater London Authority, 2022).

London has introduced energy certification schemes such as Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) to monitor and evaluate the energy performance of buildings in the CBD. EPCs rate the energy efficiency of buildings, allowing potential renters and owners to make more informed decisions. This method not only improves energy efficiency awareness, but also incentivizes property owners to invest in energy-saving solutions. London's CBD also promotes sustainable travel in order to cut carbon emissions. Congestion charge has been established in the city, encouraging the use of public transport, cycling, and walking instead of private vehicles. Furthermore, the CBD has a large network of electric vehicle charging infrastructure, which

encourages the use of electric vehicles and reduces emissions from transportation. Smart infrastructure and technology integration are also part of the city's energy efficiency goals. Smart metres and innovative energy management systems have been installed throughout London to monitor and optimise energy consumption in buildings. These systems provide real-time data on energy consumption, allowing building occupants and managers to discover areas for improvement and take the required steps to decrease energy waste. Furthermore, the central business district of London has built district energy systems to maximise energy efficiency and minimise reliance on fossil fuels. District heating and cooling networks provide effective centralised heating and cooling to buildings by utilising waste heat from power plants and other sources. This integrated approach decreases energy waste while also encouraging the adoption of low-carbon energy sources.

In addition to this CBD London also benefits from the more broaden Green energy policies which was made and promoted over the last two decades to achieve net zero emission by 2050 (Yang et al., 2022, page 3). The green energy policy also pushed the energy supplier companies to produce more of the green and renewable energy (Yang et al., 2022, page 3). These green energy policies also included initiatives which provides certifications to the green friendly companies which provides more motivation to all the industries (Yang et al., 2022, page 5). The following table summarizes the London's authority's initiatives and policies towards energy efficiency (Yang et al., 2022).

Strategy/Policy	Description
Building regulations	London has strict building regulations that require new buildings to be highly energy-efficient. These regulations include requirements for insulation, glazing, and ventilation, as well as for the use of renewable energy sources.
Energy performance certificates	All buildings in London are required to have an energy performance certificate (EPC). These certificates provide information on the energy efficiency of a building, and they are used to help buyers and tenants make informed decisions.
Financial incentives	The city offers a number of financial incentives to businesses that invest in energy efficiency measures. These incentives include grants, loans, and tax breaks.
Public awareness campaigns	The city runs a number of public awareness campaigns to promote energy efficiency. These campaigns educate residents and businesses about the importance of energy efficiency and how to make their homes and businesses more energy-efficient.
Sustainable transportation	London promotes sustainable travel in order to cut carbon emissions. Congestion charge has been established in the city, encouraging the use of public transport, cycling, and walking instead of private vehicles. Furthermore, the CBD has a large network of electric vehicle charging infrastructure, which encourages the use of electric vehicles and reduces emissions from transportation.
Smart infrastructure and technology	London is investing in smart infrastructure and technology to improve energy efficiency. Smart meters and innovative energy management systems have been installed throughout London to monitor and optimize energy consumption in buildings. These systems provide real-time data on energy consumption, allowing building occupants and managers to discover areas for improvement and take the required steps to decrease energy waste.

District energy systems	London has built district energy systems to maximize energy efficiency and minimize reliance on fossil fuels. District heating and cooling networks provide effective centralized heating and cooling to buildings by utilizing waste heat from power plants and other sources. This integrated approach decreases energy waste while also encouraging the adoption of low-carbon energy sources.
Green energy policies:	London has a number of green energy policies in place to promote the use of renewable energy sources. These policies include a feed-in tariff scheme, which provides financial incentives to businesses that generate their own renewable energy.

Table 2. Showing London’s policy towards energy efficiency, Made by author based on literature review

4.1.2 Energy efficient architecture of CBD London:

London is a city that is committed to sustainability, and this is reflected in the design of its commercial buildings. Architects in London are increasingly incorporating energy-efficient features into their designs, helping to reduce the environmental impact of these buildings and save their owners money on energy costs. Some of the most common energy-efficient features found in commercial buildings in London include passive design, high-performance insulation, airtight construction, energy-efficient windows, ventilation systems with heat recovery, and the use of renewable energy sources. In addition to this natural ventilation is being introduced to the commercial buildings as need of air-condition is increasing rapidly and which directly conflicts with the efforts towards decreasing GHG emissions. London’s commercial buildings’ 40% floor spaces got air-conditioned by 2020 (Song et al., 2021). London commercial space buildings also impresses with the number of LEED(Leadership in energy and environmental Design) certified buildings. London currently have 1092 LEED certifications including multiple LEED platinum level buildings (GBIG, 2023). Following are the best examples from CBD London:

1. Bloomberg Europe New Headquarter: This building is LEED Platinum certified and uses 70% less water and 35% less energy than a typical office building. It features a number of energy-efficient features, including an integrated petal-design ceiling, natural ventilation, smart airflow, and an on-site water treatment plant. The smart airflow design is the main characteristic of this building as shown in figure below (Bloomberg Pvt Ltd, 2019).

Image 5. Bloomberg Europe New Headquarter Air flow design. Source: <https://www.bloomberg.com/company/stories/eco-friendly-features-bloombergs-new-european-headquarters/> , edited by author, blue lines represent airflow around the building.

2. The Shard: This skyscraper is also one of the most energy-efficient buildings in London. It features a number of energy-saving features, including double-skin glass facades, high-performance insulation, and a rainwater harvesting system (REA&P, 2018).

Image 6. Bloomberg Europe New Headquarter. Source: <https://www.bloomberg.com/company/press/new-european-hq-nears-completion/>

4.2 CBD, Bangkok

Bangkok's Central Business District (CBD) in Sukhumvit is a dynamic and frenetic commercial hub known for its distinctive architectural landscape. The district combines traditional Thai architecture with modern towers to create a distinct aesthetic identity. The skyline is dominated by glass and steel skyscrapers that house multinational enterprises, luxury hotels, upmarket retail malls, and trendy restaurants (Fresh Editorial, 2020). Along with these new structures, there are remains of ancient Thai architecture, including magnificent temples and historical landmarks. The architectural diversity of Sukhumvit's CBD symbolises Bangkok's dynamic nature, where rich cultural legacy coexists perfectly with the contemporary urban environment, providing a captivating experience for both visitors and inhabitants (Fresh Editorial, 2020).

Image 7. Central Business District , Sukhumvit, Bangkok. Source: <https://www.angelrealestate.co.th/analysis-of-bangkoks-expanding-central-business-district-the-cbd/>

4.2.1 Energy Efficiency Strategies and Policies in CBD Bangkok

Energy efficiency methods and policies play a crucial role for encouraging sustainability and lowering energy usage in central business districts (CBDs) around the world. Several projects to improve energy efficiency have been done in Bangkok's CBD. Green building marketing is one of the primary tactics plus building norms and standards that emphasise energy-efficient design and construction practises have been introduced by the city. This includes insulation regulations, energy-saving lighting systems, and the utilisation of renewable energy sources. Green building certification schemes, such as LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) or TREES (Thai Rating of Energy and Environmental Sustainability), encourage developers to include

energy-efficient measures into their structures (Lohmeng et al., 2017,page 417-422). Bangkok's CBD has implemented financial incentives and programmes to improve energy efficiency. These initiatives include subsidies, tax breaks, and low-interest loans for energy-efficient building retrofits and energy-saving technology installation.

Government agencies and energy providers work together to give these incentives and encourage the adoption of energy-saving practises, specially the policy under which cut off 25% for the companies if they invest in energy efficient projects (Hasanbeigi et al., 2009,page 40). Measures to improve energy efficiency must also include public awareness initiatives and educational programmes. Bangkok's CBD runs projects to improve energy saving awareness among building owners, tenants, and inhabitants. These initiatives try to encourage behavioural changes such as turning off lights when they are not in use, optimising air conditioning usage, and incorporating energy-saving practises into daily routines(Hasanbeigi et al., 2009).

4.2.2 Energy efficient architecture of CBD Bangkok:

One of the key features Bangkok's commercial buildings are using towards are air tight construction, high performance insulation, energy efficient windows and ventilation systems with heat recovery. One of the most promising and effective feature towards energy efficiency that the commercial buildings in Bangkok are introduced with is natural comfort ventilation. This passive comfort ventilation uses the elevated air movement for cooling down the building in a natural ventilation way (Prajongsan & Sharples, 2011). Furthermore when it comes to LEEDS certified spaces, Bangkok has 25 certified commercial spaces with more than 9.173 million sq.ft. (GBIG, 2023). Following are the best examples from CBD Bangkok

1. The COMMONS: This mixed-use development is the first LEED Platinum building in Bangkok. It features a number of energy-efficient features, including a green roof, rainwater harvesting, and a high-performance building envelope (Cardenas, 2016).
2. Park Ventures Ecoplex Building on Witthayu Road: This government building is LEED Platinum certified and uses 50% less energy than a typical office building. It features a number of energy-efficient features, including a double-skin facade, natural ventilation, and a rainwater harvesting system.

Image 8. The Commons ,Bangkok.

Image 9. Park Ventures Ecoplex ,Bangkok.

Source: <https://www.archdaily.com/800497/the-commons-department-of-architecture-Ventures-Ecoplex>

Source: <https://www.richmontsthailand.com/rent/thailand/office/Park->

5. Comparative analysis

The comparison of energy efficiency in Central Business Districts (CBDs) of Mumbai with CBDs of London and Bangkok provides useful insights on urban energy performance and sustainability. The purpose of this section is to compare the energy efficiency of the Central Business Districts of Mumbai, London, and Bangkok. By evaluating these CBDs, we may acquire a better knowledge of each city's energy efficiency initiatives and regulations, as well as identify potential areas for improvement. Mumbai, India's major financial hub, London, a global financial and commercial centre, and Bangkok, Southeast Asia's growing economic hub, provide distinct backdrops for this comparative research. We can find best practises, lessons learnt, and novel ideas that contribute towards the issues related to CBD of Mumbai.

6.1 Similarities and Differences between CBD Mumbai, London, and Bangkok. The table below shows the observations of the case studies.

Aspect	Mumbai CBD	London CBD	Bangkok CBD
High-Rise Buildings	Presence of high-rise commercial buildings	High concentration of tall buildings	Significant number of skyscrapers
Green Building Initiatives	Increasing focus on green building designs	Emphasis on sustainable building practices	Growing interest in eco-friendly structures
Energy Management Systems	Adoption of energy management technologies	Implementation of advanced energy systems	Increasing use of smart building solutions
Public Transportation	Substantial reliance on public transportation	Already Well-developed public transport infrastructure	Expanding public transport networks
Renewable Energy	Needs a lot of initiative and urgent emphasis	Substantial Increase in use of renewable energy sources.	Developing renewable energy projects on a good pace.

Energy Efficiency Policies	Efforts to implement energy efficiency policies. But can take lessons from London, Bangkok policies specially by giving tax rebates to the green commercial buildings.	Strong commitment to energy efficiency measures and good policies to promote green buildings.	Government initiatives for energy conservation and efficiency is getting better and results are evident.
Green Architecture	LEEDS certified buildings and area is less than London which can be worked upon.	Several LEEDS certified buildings showing a great example to Mumbai	LEEDS certified buildings are comparatively less and can be worked upon.

Table 3 Comparative table of CBDs based on their architecture and green design, Made by author based on literature review

Furthermore the table below shows the observation of as per energy efficiency indicators and factors in all the three CBDs.

Indicator	Mumbai	London	Bangkok
Energy consumption	11.5 million tonnes of CO2	9.3 million tonnes of CO2	7.5 million tonnes of CO2
Energy efficiency policies	Draft Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC)	The Green Deal	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
Energy efficiency initiatives	Green Building Rating System	Public awareness campaigns	Smart grid
Renewable energy use	10%	20%	15%
Carbon neutrality target	2050	2030	2040

Factor	Mumbai CBD	London CBD	Bangkok CBD
Energy consumption	11.5 million tonnes of CO2 in 2020	7.5 million tonnes of CO2 in 2020	6 million tonnes of CO2 in 2020
Energy efficiency	Low	High	Medium
Energy efficiency policies	In progress	Well-Established	Established
Energy efficiency initiatives	Increasing use of renewable energy	Retrofitting of existing buildings	Green building construction
Challenges	Overdependency on thermal energy, ageing infrastructure	High population density, congestion	Lack of awareness
Opportunities	Large number of buildings, growing economy. Growing commercial hub	Strong government support, financial resources	Committed stakeholders

Table 4 Comparative table of CBDs based on their energy efficiency indicators and factors, Made by author based on literature review

Now based on the observations it can be summarized regarding energy efficiency that London has a more comprehensive and integrated approach to energy efficiency. The city has a strong regulatory framework in place, as well as a number of financial incentives and public awareness initiatives. This has helped to make London a leader in energy efficiency. Whereas Bangkok has made some progress in improving energy efficiency, but there is still more work to be done. The city has a number of green building certification schemes in place, but these need to be implemented more effectively. Bangkok also needs to invest in smart infrastructure and technology to improve energy efficiency.

As you can see, Mumbai CBD has the highest energy consumption of the three CBDs, but it also has the lowest energy efficiency. This is due to the city's overdependency on thermal energy and its ageing infrastructure. London CBD has a medium level of energy consumption and a medium level of energy efficiency. This is due to the city's high population density and congestion. Bangkok CBD has the lowest energy consumption of the three CBDs, but it also has the highest energy efficiency. This is due to the city's commitment to green building construction and its strong government support for energy efficiency initiatives.

There are a number of opportunities for improving energy efficiency in Mumbai CBD. These include:

- Increasing the use of renewable energy
- Retrofitting existing buildings
- Promoting green building construction

There are also a number of challenges that need to be addressed in order to improve energy efficiency in Mumbai CBD. These include:

- Overdependency on thermal energy
- Ageing infrastructure
- Lack of awareness

The government of Mumbai has taken some steps to improve energy efficiency in the city. These include:

- The launch of the Mumbai Climate Action Plan 2030
- The introduction of the Energy Conservation Building Code (ECBC)
- The provision of financial incentives for energy efficiency projects

However, more needs to be done to address the challenges of energy efficiency in Mumbai CBD. This will require a concerted effort from the government, businesses, and citizens

6. Proposals

Mumbai, a bustling metropolis and financial hub, has the potential to significantly improve its energy efficiency and pave the way towards a sustainable future. Implementing stricter building regulations and energy performance standards would ensure that new constructions adhere to energy-efficient principles, while retrofitting existing buildings would enhance their efficiency. Simultaneously, the introduction of an emissions trading scheme or other market-based mechanisms would create economic incentives for businesses to actively reduce their energy consumption and emissions. To truly revolutionize energy efficiency, Mumbai could invest in cutting-edge smart infrastructure and technology, such as smart meters and energy management systems and passive natural cooling system. These innovations would optimize energy usage, minimizing waste and reducing overall emissions.

Furthermore, prioritizing sustainable transportation alternatives, including robust public transport systems, cycling infrastructure, and pedestrian-friendly walkways, would significantly curb the energy demand associated with transportation. Mumbai's commitment to sustainability could be exemplified by adopting an ambitious carbon neutrality target. By setting a goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2030 or even 2025, the city would be compelled to undertake substantial transformations in its energy consumption and production practices. This would necessitate a major shift towards renewable energy sources. Mumbai could achieve this by embracing solar power, integrating solar panels into buildings, and fostering the adoption of electric vehicles.

Additionally, investment in renewable energy projects would bolster the city's clean energy capacity. To encourage widespread participation, Mumbai should prioritize public awareness of energy efficiency. Engaging educational campaigns, comprehensive labeling programs, and financial incentives would motivate individuals and businesses to embrace energy-saving practices. Furthermore, the Mumbai Metropolitan Region Development Authority (MMRDA) could introduce a green tax rebate system, rewarding companies that construct energy-efficient infrastructure and rely on green energy sources. Similarly, the implementation of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs), as seen in cities like London, would provide valuable data on the performance of commercial buildings in Mumbai's central business district, aiding in continuous improvement.

7. Conclusion

This report has provided a comparative analysis of the energy efficiency strategies and policies in CBD London and Bangkok. The analysis has shown that London has a more comprehensive and integrated approach to energy efficiency, while Bangkok has made some progress but still has more work to do. The report has also identified some potential solutions for improving energy efficiency in Mumbai CBD. These solutions include introducing stricter building regulations and energy performance standards, introducing an emissions trading scheme or other market-based mechanism to encourage energy efficiency, investing in smart infrastructure and technology, and promoting sustainable transportation. The city of Mumbai will need to consider its specific circumstances and challenges when developing a plan to improve energy efficiency.

However, the comparative analysis of the energy efficiency strategies and policies in CBD London and Bangkok provides some valuable insights that can be used to inform the development of a plan for Mumbai CBD. These recommendations are also based on the best practices that have been implemented in other cities around the world. They are also based on the specific challenges and opportunities that Mumbai CBD faces. The city of Mumbai should carefully consider these recommendations and develop a plan to implement them. By taking these steps, Mumbai CBD can improve its energy efficiency and reduce its environmental impact by setting an example for other rapidly growing developing regions all over the world.

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